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RHEOLOGY OF MIXTURES OF 1-PHENYL 1,2-DICHLOROETHANE WITH BUTADIENE-NITRILE RUBBER AND STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF THEIR COMPOSITIONS

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Abstract

In this scientific study, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and NBR-40 butadiene-nitrile rubber-based compounds resistant to aggressive environments were prepared. First, the rheology was studied by preparing binary mixtures with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane and NBR-40, and the optimal amount and processing conditions required to contain 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane were determined. Second, vulcanizates based on a special recipe containing NBR-40 with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane were obtained and their physical and mechanical properties were examined. It has been found that the addition of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane improves the physical and mechanical properties of a series of compounds.

Keywords: nitrile-butadiene rubber, 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane, rheology, modification, elastomers, infrared spectroscopy, physical and mechanical properties, functional rubber, special purpose polymer, polymer composites

Introduction

Butadiene-nitrile rubber is the main productive material for the production of rubber with high resistance to petroleum products and other aggressive media. The synthetic polymer is a product of the copolymerization of butadiene with acrylonitrile (ACN). The properties of the copolymer depend on the amount of ACN in the polymer, that is, the higher it is, the higher its resistance to oils, but the lower its elasticity.

Butadiene-nitrile rubber-based elastomeric materials are widely used in the oil industry for the production of sealants of various aggregates (such as seals, grommets etc.) operating in harsh conditions. Since the modification of butadiene-nitrile rubber (NBR) by means of compounds with different functional groups seems perspective, the structure of the butadiene-nitrile rubber is intentionally altered by the inclusion of chloride-containing compounds [1]. Such additives improve co-assimilation of polymers in the contact area between polymer phases and prevent phase separation [2].

Studies were carried out by including 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane, a functional group compound, in the composition based on butadiene-nitrile rubber [3]. First, the rheology of their binary mixtures was studied depending on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane included in butadiene-nitrile rubber, and the optimal processing regime was determined [4]. Then, the degree of influence of the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in compositions based on NBR/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on the properties of elasticity-strength, strength of metal bonds, etc. was studied.

Experimental part

In this study, a binary system was prepared by mechanically mixing different proportions of butadiene-nitrile rubber (NBR-40) with 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane on a micro laboratory two-roll mill at 40-50 °C for 5-8 minutes (Table 1). NBR-40 is a trademark of butadiene-nitrile rubber which contain nearly 40% of ACN.

Table 1.

Composition of NBR-40/1- phenyl 1,2 - dichloroethane binary mixtures by mass portions (m.p.)

No	Code of the mixture						
	Components	1Z	2Z	3Z	4Z	5Z	6Z
1	NBR-40	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane	-	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10
	Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Graphic curves were created depending on the displacement rate ($\log \dot{\gamma}$) and displacement stresses ($\log \tau$ (50403; 89431; 111886; 139834 Pa)) of the alloys of the binary mixtures prepared at temperatures of 100, 120, 150 and 170 °C (Results and their discussion section Figure.2-5). Thus, as a result of studying the rheology of binary mixtures, the optimal processing mode was determined [5,6].

The dependence of the effective viscosity of alloys ($\log \eta_{ef}$) on the displacement stress ($\log \tau$) of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixtures under

the influence of the above temperatures and stresses was studied [7].

Next NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane-96/4 binary mixture was kept in the chamber of IIRT-5 device in vulcanization mode at 153° C temperature for 20 minutes[8]. Then vulcanizate was extracted in carbon tetrachloride solvent for 24 hours and dried to constant weight. After that, infrared spectroscopic analysis was studied and it was observed that chlorine was chemically binds to the macromolecule of butadiene-nitrile rubber in a 750 cm⁻¹ absorption band (peak) (Figure 1) [9].

Figure 1. Containing 4 m.p. IR spectrum of NBR-40 sample containing 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane

The composites based on NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures (Table 2) was prepared on a two-roll mill at 30-40 °C for 25 minutes and vulcanized at 153° C for 20 minutes.

Table 2.

Composition based on a mixture of butadiene-nitrile rubber with 1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane

№	Code of the mixture						
	Components	1Z	2Z	3Z	4Z	5Z	6Z
1	NBR-40	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane	-	2	4	6	8	10
3	Sulfur	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
4	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
5	Dibenzothiazole disulfide	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
6	ZnO	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
7	Neaozone D	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
8	Stearic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
9	Rosin (colophony)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
10	Mazut	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
11	Carbon black	P-803	20	20	20	20	20
		P-324	50	50	50	50	50
	Total	187	187	187	187	187	187

The number of cross-links was determined by the equilibrium swelling method.

Physical and mechanical properties of compositions based on vulcanized NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures were studied [10].

Results and its discussion

As a result of the research, graphical curves of the displacement rate ($\log \dot{\gamma}$) and displacement stresses ($\log \tau$) of alloys of binary mixtures based on NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane at different temperatures (100-170° C) were constructed (Figure 2-5).

Analysis of the curves shows that the flow of alloys of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures

is non-Newtonian. The abnormal viscosity of the mixture is in the range $\alpha = \frac{\log \dot{\gamma}}{\log \tau} = 2,2 = 3,0$. The viscosity of NBR-40 is characterized by a lower molecular weight of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane, which is higher (ie high flow rate) than the viscosity of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the temperature range (100-170 °C). When the NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture contains 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane (2-6 k.h.), the displacement stress acting on the alloy is $\log \tau = 4.7024$ Pa and $\log \tau = 5.0488$ Pa. When the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the mixture is more than 6 mass portions (m.p.), the displacement

rate of the alloy increases monotonically, the displacement rate of the alloy increases by leaps. This is due to the fact that 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in this mixture is more than 6 m.p. and the increase in stress acting on the alloy of the mixture to the rapid destruction of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture (Figure 4). The study con-

cluded that the addition of 2-6 m.p. of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in a mixture of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane in the temperature range of 100-150° C is considered appropriate, ie it creates a cross-linking by creating structural changes in NBR-40 rubbers, accelerates the destruction process in the system when 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane is taken more than 6 m.p., the flow rate of the alloy increases sharply.

Figure 1 and Figure 2. Dependence of displacement rate on displacement stress (at 100°C (Figure 1.) and 120°C (Figure 2.) temperatures

Figure 3. and Figure 4. Dependence of displacement rate on displacement stress (at 150°C (Figure 3.) and 170°C (Figure 4.) temperatures

At 170° C, at any ratio of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture and at any value of displacement stress, the displacement rate of the alloy of the mixture decreases sharply to the flow rate of butadiene-nitrile rubber alloy to a high elastic state (h.e.s.), ie as the process takes place, the flow decreases sharply (Figure. 5). It is not advisable to process the mixture at 170° C.

In order to show more clearly the above results, the dependence of the effective viscosity of alloys ($\log \zeta_{ef}$) on the displacement stress ($\log \tau$) of NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane binary mixtures under the influence of different temperatures and stresses was studied and graph curves were constructed (Figure 6-9).

Figure 6 and Figure 7. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement stress (100 ° C Figure 6) (120 ° C Figure 7.)

Figure 8 and Figure 9. Dependence of effective viscosity on displacement stress (150 ° C Figure 8.) (170 ° C Figure 9.)

Physical and mechanical properties of compositions based on NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixture were studied (Table 3).

Table 3.

Physical and mechanical properties of compositions based on NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane mixtures

№	Properties	Code of the mixture						
		1Z	2Z	3Z	4Z	5Z	6Z	
1	Tensile strength at break, MPa	18.0	18.2	18.7	19.2	19.6	18.9	
2	100% elongation strength, MPa	6.7	6.7	7.2	7.5	7.2	6.9	
3	Relative stretch, %	330	340	345	350	360	370	
4	Relative residual deformation, %	13.1	13.1	13.0	12.8	13.9	15.2	
5	Tear resistance, kN/m	65,0	64,9	66,5	67,6	67,9	68,4	
6	Metal contact strength, Mpa	Steel 3	5,6	5,7	6,5	7,2	7,4	7,9
		Brass	6,3	6,6	7,5	8,9	9,5	9,6
7	Abrasion resistance, $\text{sm}^3/\text{kVt saat}$	58,7	58,1	57,5	57,4	57,0	56,8	
8	Hardness by TM-2 device, c.u	82	81,8	80,3	80	79,6	79	
9	Elasticity on the back leap, %	9,1	9,4	9,8	10,2	10,1	9,8	
10	Swelling rate at 296 K temperature for 25 hours,%	Gasoline	4,9	4,2	3,8	3,0	3,0	2,8
		Gasoline:benzene - 3:1	16,9	16,0	15,0	13,6	13,0	12,9
11	Coefficients of aging from heat at 379 K temperature for 50 hours,%	ϵ_1	0,81	0,81	0,83	0,84	0,83	0,80
		ϵ_2	0,62	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,61

Graphical curves on a number of properties such as Tensile strength at break, Metal contact strength and Relative stretch have been constructed in order to show the obtained results more clearly.

Figure 10. Dependence of breaking strength of vulcanizates on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane

Figure 11. Dependence of metal contact strength of vulcanizates on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane

Figure 11. Dependence of relative stretch of vulcanizates on the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane

As a result of the study, it was determined that a number of physical and mechanical properties of the composition improved when the amount of 1-phenyl 1,2 dichloroethane in the mixture was up to 6 m.p.: Tensile strength at break 18,0 MPa against 19,5 MPa; Tear resistance 65 kN/m against 67,6 kN/m; Metal contact strength: With steel: 5,6 MPa against 7,0 Mpa; With brass: 6,3 MPa against 8,9 Mpa; Swelling rate in gasoline:benzene - 3:1 solvent 16,9% against 13,6% and so on properties have improved.

Thus, as a result of the research, NBR-40/1-phenyl 1,2-dichloroethane 98-94/2-6 mixtures can be used in the production of long-lasting elastomeric materials under aggressive conditions.

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